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THE INFLUENCE OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SOUTHERN NEW HAMPSHIRE UNIVERSITY'S PROGRAM IN KAKUMA REFUGEE CAMP, TURKANA WEST, KENYA

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ABSTRACT

Study sought to investigate the influence of stakeholder management practices on performance of Southern New Hampshire University Programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp, Turkana West Kenya. The study was guided by the following objectives; to examine the influence of stakeholder communication on the performance of Southern New Hampshire University programme, to assess the influence of stakeholder identification on the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme, to examine the influence of stakeholder engagement on the performance of Southern New Hampshire University and to analyze the influence of stakeholder empowerment on the performance of Southern New Hampshire University. The study was anchored on Stakeholder Theory and Institutional Theory. This study employed a mixed method approach using convergent parallel design. The study targeted 105 participants comprising of 98 enrolled students, 5 administrators and 2 CUE staff. Census and purposive sampling was used to ensure that all key stakeholders and students were represented. The study used both quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 26, applying descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, multiple regression, and ANOVA to assess relationships between variables. Qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis, where recurring themes were identified, coded, and interpreted to complement the quantitative findings. The study found that stakeholder communication significantly influenced the performance of SNHU in Kakuma Refugee Camp, with over 70% of respondents confirming that communication was timely, transparent, and trust-building, though some noted delays in routine updates. On stakeholder identification, most respondents agreed that structured criteria guided selection and participation (M = 3.88), though evolving interests were not always fully considered. Stakeholder engagement was generally strong, with about two-thirds of respondents acknowledging involvement in decision-making and collaboration (M = 3.92). However, gaps remained in inclusivity and equitable access to services. Regarding empowerment, many stakeholders felt equipped to participate in risk management and policy awareness (M = 3.85), but some cited limited influence over practical decision-making. The study recommends that SNHU should prioritize strengthening student support services to enhance accessibility and responsiveness while sustaining high performance in academics, skills application, and community acceptance.

Keywords:- Stakeholder management practices, Stakeholder Communication channels, Stakeholder Identification, Stakeholder engagement, Stakeholder Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

University programs implemented in refugee contexts play a critical role in advancing access to higher education, fostering resilience, and contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals (UNHCR, 2022). These programs are increasingly recognized as vital tools in addressing inequalities, promoting self-reliance, and enhancing socio-economic opportunities for displaced populations. However, the performance of such programs has raised concerns globally, with challenges related to resource allocation, accessibility, and integration into local communities. International organizations such as UNHCR, the World Bank, and various universities have long recognized the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in refugee education programs. These

collaborations bring together governments, educational institutions, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and local communities to ensure the success and sustainability of such initiatives. Stakeholder management practices, particularly communication, engagement, and empowerment, directly influence program outcomes by improving resource allocation, ensuring inclusivity, and enhancing the delivery of education. However, fragmented communication and inadequate stakeholder engagement often hinder the effectiveness of these programs (Taylor et al., 2022).

In Africa, similar trends can be observed in refugee education programs. Countries like Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Tanzania have implemented higher education initiatives for refugees, supported by partnerships between national

governments, international universities, and agencies like UNHCR. These initiatives have expanded access to learning resources and provided refugees with opportunities to join degree-awarding institutions (Abebe, 2023). However, weaknesses in stakeholder identification, communication, and engagement have often slowed decision-making processes and hindered program efficiency. In Ethiopia, for instance, bureaucratic hurdles and insufficient coordination between stakeholders have delayed the implementation of educational programs for refugees (Anteneh & Melak, 2024).

Nigeria's situation highlights the increased demand for higher education among internally displaced persons (IDPs), a result of conflict-induced displacement. Various stakeholders, including universities, government agencies, and private sector actors, have responded by offering a mix of online, distance, and vocational programs (Okafor & Eze, 2020). However, ineffective communication between federal regulators and partner institutions has created inconsistencies in program accreditation, credit transfer, and curriculum alignment. These challenges have limited the opportunities for IDP learners to progress academically and integrate into the broader educational system (Ogunyemi, 2021).

Tanzania, another African country with a significant refugee population, has seen higher education provision expand within refugee camps like Nyarugusu and Nduta. These programs rely heavily on effective stakeholder management practices. However, fragmented communication channels and gaps in stakeholder engagement have undermined the performance of these initiatives. Stakeholder identification and participation remain problematic, particularly in ensuring that marginalized groups, such as women and students with special needs, are adequately included in decision-making processes (Lupogo, 2020). Furthermore, underfunded empowerment initiatives, such as student councils and peer mentoring programs, limit the agency of stakeholders, reducing their ability to influence decisions that affect their education (Mkude & Haji, 2022).

Kenya's experience, particularly at Kakuma Refugee Camp, further exemplifies these challenges. The Kakuma Refugee Camp, located in Turkana County, is home to a large number of refugees, and its education programs are supported by a range of stakeholders, including the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the Kenyan government, NGOs, and universities. While these stakeholders are involved in education delivery from pre-

primary to tertiary levels, challenges related to stakeholder management persist. Limited inclusivity in decision-making often sidelines marginalized groups, such as women, youth, and community-based leaders, which affects the overall effectiveness of the programs (Ivana, 2022). Weak accountability structures have also led to fragmented planning and delayed resource allocation, ultimately impacting program performance and learner outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Academic mobility and the integration of foreign degrees into local systems are increasingly critical to higher education internationalization and student transitions between universities. These processes directly influence student satisfaction, which in turn affects programme performance indicators such as retention, graduation rates, reputation, and overall academic outcomes (Jain & Varsha, 2024). However, ensuring that academic mobility contributes positively to programme performance requires effective coordination among multiple stakeholders, particularly in contexts where higher education initiatives intersect with local systems. In Kenya, evidence shows that weak stakeholder management often undermines the performance of education and

development initiatives, particularly in marginalized and resource-constrained contexts (Nderitu & Karanja, 2022). In Kakuma, where multiple actors influence education delivery, the lack of coordinated engagement has at times resulted in duplication of efforts, resource inefficiencies, and reduced trust among stakeholders (Mwangi & Wanjiru, 2023). This situation mirrors findings in other marginalized areas, where stakeholder exclusion or poor communication has negatively affected project outcomes (Kamau & Muriithi, 2022). For the SNHU programme, the absence of a clear assessment of how stakeholder management practices influence its performance raises concerns about sustainability and long-term impact in the refugee camp. Despite recognition of foreign degrees by Kenya's Commission for University Education, many graduates in Southern New Hampshire University Programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp still struggle with credit transfer, academic progression, and acceptance into local institutions (Murray & Höhn, 2023). Thus, this study sought to assess the influence of stakeholder management practices on performance of Southern New Hampshire University Programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp, Turkana West Kenya.

Conceptual framework

LITERATURE REVIEW

Stakeholder Theory

The Stakeholder Theory was first introduced by Freeman (1984) as a framework for understanding how organizations interact with and depend on their stakeholders. It emphasizes that the success of an institution is not solely determined by its internal resources or shareholders but also by its ability to effectively manage relationships with diverse groups that influence or are influenced by its activities. According to Harrison, Barney, Freeman, and Phillips (2019), organizations that prioritize stakeholder needs, values, and engagement are more likely to achieve sustainable performance. Key constructs of Stakeholder Theory include stakeholder identification, communication, engagement, and empowerment. In the context of higher education programs such as the Southern New Hampshire University initiative in Kakuma Refugee Camp, stakeholders comprise regulatory bodies like the Commission for University Education, local universities, employers, refugees, host communities, and international partners. Effective management of these groups ensures inclusivity, program sustainability, and enhanced outcomes for learners (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). Stakeholder identification is a crucial element of this theory. Clarkson (1995) argues that organizations must distinguish between primary stakeholders, who are essential for survival, and secondary stakeholders, who influence

operations indirectly. For SNHU in Kakuma, primary stakeholders include learners (refugees), regulatory authorities, and donors, while secondary stakeholders include local NGOs and employers. Properly identifying these actors clarifies expectations and fosters a collaborative approach that minimizes conflict and enhances program alignment with local and international standards (Mitchell, Agle, & Wood, 1997). Another critical component of Stakeholder Theory is communication. Transparent and inclusive communication channels ensure that stakeholders remain informed and actively contribute to program development. In multi-diverse environments such as Kakuma, where cultural and socio-economic differences are pronounced, effective communication fosters trust and inclusivity. This aligns with Bryson (2018), who emphasizes that dialogue and negotiation are vital in environments where interests often conflict. Stakeholder engagement is also central to the theory. Engaging diverse actors creates opportunities for co-creation, joint decision-making, and mutual accountability. In the case of SNHU’s program in Kakuma, stakeholder engagement involves incorporating refugees’ voices in curriculum adaptation, involving employers in aligning training with labor market demands, and partnering with local universities to ensure academic recognition. Such practices strengthen ownership and increase the likelihood of program sustainability (Friedman & Miles, 2006). Empowerment, as emphasized by Freeman et al. (2010), refers to the process of enabling stakeholders to influence

decisions and benefit meaningfully from organizational outcomes. For SNHU in Kakuma, empowering learners and local communities through skills development, career opportunities, and access to higher education enhances both program legitimacy and socio-economic transformation. This resonates with the broader goals of Kenya’s Vision 2030 social pillar and SDG 4, which advocate for inclusive and equitable quality education.

Stakeholder theory has been criticized for giving excessive importance to the role of government in promoting certain morally significant social values. This is done by assuming that some institutions are inherently better suited to fulfill specific stakeholder-related values, while leaving other institutions to address different dimensions. A more complex issue is that stakeholder’s theory often fails to clearly define the government’s role in advancing stakeholder interests. Notably, it struggles to explain how the interests of marginalized stakeholders are protected within the framework of stakeholder management (Hargrave & Smith, 2025).

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study area refers to the specific geographic location where research is conducted, providing the context within which the phenomena under study occur (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019). For this study, the research was conducted at Southern New Hampshire University in Kakuma Refugee Camp, located in Turkana West, Kenya. Kakuma is one of the largest refugee settlements in Kenya, hosting refugees from countries such as South Sudan, Somalia, Ethiopia, and the Democratic Republic of Congo. The camp is governed by multiple stakeholders, including the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, the Kenyan government, and local host authorities, creating a complex governance and operational environment. SNHU operates higher education programmes within Kakuma, providing refugees with opportunities to pursue undergraduate and diploma-level studies. The institution uses a mastery-based grading system that emphasizes learning outcomes and student progression

rather than traditional letter grades. This system aims to facilitate academic mobility and alignment with international educational standards, but it also introduces unique challenges in communication, stakeholder coordination, and adaptation to local educational norms.

Target Population

According to Pathfinder (2025), the Kakuma Refugee Camp hosts 7,365 refugees, including those who participate in various educational programs such as those offered by Southern New Hampshire University. However, not all of these refugees are enrolled in the SNHU program. The study specifically focuses on individuals directly involved with the SNHU programme, including students currently enrolled, SNHU administrators, and Commission for University Education staff who oversee accreditation and compliance.

Based on information obtained from the SNHU office in Kakuma, the SNHU program had 98 enrolled students, supported by 5 administrators and 2 CUE staff, making a total target population of 105 participants. This population represents all individuals who are directly engaged in or affected by the SNHU program, rather than the total refugee population in Kakuma.

Focusing on this specific population ensures that the study gathers data from those with first-hand experience and direct involvement in the SNHU program. It also allows for a comprehensive assessment of stakeholder management practices, as all students can be included through a census technique, while administrators and CUE staff, being fewer in number but key to understanding program oversight, are purposively selected for qualitative interviews. This approach ensures the study collects relevant and meaningful data to address the research objectives effectively.

Table 3.1: Target Population

Category	Target Respondents
SNHU administrators	5
Commission for University Education staff	2
Students	98
Total	105

Source :Path finder (2025)

Sampling Size and Sampling Procedure

Sampling involves selecting a representative subset of the population to collect data that reflects the characteristics of the entire group (Verma & Verma, 2020 ; Levy & Goldfarb, 2021). The sample size should be sufficient to capture the main features of the population and provide reliable insights for the study (Verma & Verma, 2020).

Sampling Size

In this study, the total SNHU program population comprised 98 students, 5 administrators, and 2 Commission for University Education staff, totaling 105 individuals. Given the small size of the student population, all students were included using a census approach. Administrators and CUE staff were selected purposively due to their specialized knowledge and direct involvement in program management.

Sampling Procedure

This combination of census and purposive sampling ensured that all key stakeholders were represented, providing comprehensive insights into stakeholder management practices and program performance. The approach allowed the researcher to gather in-depth, relevant, and meaningful data from participants who are directly engaged in or knowledgeable about the SNHU program and its stakeholder management processes.

Data Collection instruments

Data collection involves obtaining information from study participants (Taherdoost, 2021). The accuracy and reliability of the collected data largely depend on the tools and techniques used during the process (Gatuyu & Kinyua, 2020). Data collection instruments, on the other hand, refer to the specific tools utilized to gather relevant information (Sharma, 2022). The study used questionnaires in collecting data from students and interview guides was used in collecting data from from cue staff and SNHU administrators.

Pilot Testing of the Instruments

The pilot study aims to test the feasibility and effectiveness of the research instruments (questionnaires and interview guide questions) to ensure they collect relevant and reliable data. It also

helped identify any uncertainties or misunderstandings in the questions, allowing for necessary revisions before the full-scale study. Feedback from the pilot study informed necessary modifications to enhance clarity and effectiveness before data collection. (Anesthesiol, 2017) . Therefore, the researcher used 10% of the total sample size 105 which was 11 respondents to run a preliminary study of all the instruments at Jesuit Worldwide Learning at Kakuma refugee camp, and they did not participate in data collection (Omair,2025). Before data collection starts to check the reliability and functionality of research questionnaires.

Validity of the Instrument

This refers to the extent to which a concept or measurement is well founded and correspond accurately to the real world. Ensuring questions comprehensively cover all aspects of stakeholder management practices and project performance. The two university supervisors and 5 more lecturers in the field of project management was contacted to confirm the validity of the research instrument to ensure the content and construction of the instrument. Therefore, based on the supervisors and researcher agreement the correction was made ensuring reliability of instruments (Elhambakhsh 2024).

The validity of the research instrument was assessed through content validity during the pilot study. To ensure that the questionnaire accurately measured the intended constructs, the study employed expert judgment to assess content validity. A panel of 7 subject-matter experts, including professionals in education, programme evaluation, and stakeholder management, was consulted to evaluate the relevance of each item in the research instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the reliability of the instrument used, university supervisors and expert judgment was contact dependability audit to examine the process and data, code- recode strategy was used to compare and confirm the results. The researcher then used Cronbach alpha, by Lee Cronbach in (1951) which is the statistic that holds 0.7 or up to 1 acceptable reliability and it's used to assess the internal consistency of instruments used (Abd & Rahman 2024).

During the pilot study, a total of 7 questionnaires were administered. Out of these, all 7 were successfully completed and returned, resulting in a response rate of 100%. This high response rate reflected the participants' willingness to engage with the study and provided sufficient feedback to refine the questionnaire for improved clarity, structure, and relevance ahead of the main data collection. Cronbach's Alpha was adopted to evaluate the internal consistency of the instrument and the results are as presented. A threshold of 0.7 or above was used to determine reliability (Taber, 2018).

Data Collection Procedures

In data Collection Procedures, this study was guided by convergent parallel design. According to Kothari (2019), convergent parallel design entails quantitative and qualitative data are collected concurrently. Both types of data are analyzed separately but integrated during the interpretation phase to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. The rationale for using this design is to obtain broad numeric trends through questionnaire and then explore these findings in depth through interviews, thereby enriching the overall interpretation of the research problem.

Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained an introductory letter from the Catholic University of Eastern Africa.

This letter was presented to the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) to secure a formal research permit.

Upon getting approval from the university and NACOSTI to proceed with data collection and in accordance with government policy, the researcher also consulted relevant public officials where the study was conducted. An introductory letter was prepared before heading to the field for data collection. With these preparations in place, the researcher proceeded to distribute questionnaires using the drop-and-pick technique, allowing respondents ample time to review the questions. The study employed self-administered questionnaires as the primary research instrument to gather data from respondents. The researcher also scheduled appointments with key stakeholders to facilitate the distribution of the questionnaires and to book appointments for interviews with administrators. Data collection and analysis occurred concurrently,

ensuring that the ongoing analysis informed the sampling and data collection strategies.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis involves systematically organizing, interpreting, and examining collected data to extract meaningful patterns and insights that inform conclusions and decision-making (Moreira et al., 2019). In this study, both quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed separately, in line with the convergent parallel design, and later integrated during interpretation to provide a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder management practices and

their influence on SNHU program performance in Kakuma Refugee Camp.

Quantitative data collected from student questionnaires were coded and entered into SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize respondents'

views on stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment, as well as on the performance

of the SNHU program. These measures provided an overall picture of trends and patterns within the dataset,

allowing for easy visualization and comparison of key variable.

To assess the relationships between the independent variables stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment and the dependent variable, program performance, multiple analytical approaches were applied. Pearson correlation analysis was first conducted to determine the strength and direction of associations between each stakeholder management dimension and program performance. This helped to identify which aspects of stakeholder management were significantly related to program outcomes.

In addition, multiple regression analysis was employed to evaluate the combined effect of all stakeholder management dimensions on program performance. The regression model used was expressed as $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon$, where Y represented the performance of the SNHU program, X1 to X4 represented stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment,

respectively, β_0 was the intercept, and ϵ was the error term. This analysis allowed for determining both the individual and collective contributions of the independent variables in explaining variations in program performance.

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was further conducted to test the overall significance of the regression model. This step ensured that the set of independent variables collectively predicted program performance and confirmed the reliability of the model before interpreting individual predictors. The combination of correlation, regression, and ANOVA provided both a detailed and holistic understanding of how stakeholder management practices influenced program outcomes.

Qualitative data from interviews with SNHU administrators and CUE staff were analyzed using thematic analysis.

Interview transcripts were reviewed to identify recurring themes and patterns related to stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, empowerment, and program performance. Themes were coded, organized, and interpreted to provide contextual insights that complemented the quantitative findings. Direct quotations were included where necessary to highlight nuanced perspectives and to ensure authenticity in representing stakeholder experiences.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Rate of Response

The study determined the total number of participants who actively engaged in this study by completing and submitting the questionnaires, as well as those who participated in interviews. The response rate analysis was presented in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Population Type	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Students		
Response	95 out of 98	96.9%
SNHU Administrators		
Response	5 out of 5	100%
CUE Staff		
Response	2 out of 2	100%
Total	102	97.1%

Data presented in Table 4.1 shows that out of 98 questionnaires that were distributed to 98 student’s respondents, 95 questionnaires were correctly completed, sent back, and deemed appropriate for analysis which translated to a 96.9% response rate on questionnaire.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Distribution of Respondents by Role at the College

This subsection presents the categorization of respondents based on their current role within the SNHU learning ecosystem at Kakuma Refugee Camp or within the Commission for University Education. Respondents were asked to indicate their role at the college and the findings were presented in Figure 4.1 below.

Figure 2 : Respondents by Role at the College

The results in Figure 4.1 shows that the majority of respondents, 57 (55.9%), were enrolled in Southern New

Hampshire University’s Global Education Movement programs. This conclusion emphasizes the importance of

students as main stakeholders and beneficiaries of the university’s educational endeavors in Kakuma Refugee Camp.

Furthermore, 14 respondents (13.7%) claimed that they handle logistics, demonstrating a strong operational support presence within the college structure. These professionals are critical to the efficient delivery of learning services and day-to-day operations. The number of respondents who handle the day-to-day operations of SNHU programs in

Kakuma was 11 (10.8%). This group is responsible for strategic program coordination, resource planning, and stakeholder communication.

Distribution of Respondents by the Number of Years in the College

This segment shows how responders are distributed based on how long they have been affiliated with the college. The distribution is shown in Figure 4.2 below.

Figure 4.2: Number of Years in the College

The results in Figure 4.2 shows that the majority of respondents, 46 (41.1%), reported being linked with the college for between 4-6 years, 32(28.6%) had been in the college for a period between 1-3 years. Most participants have a high level of experience and continuous engagement, which suggests that their replies are based on extensive exposure to the college’s stakeholder practices, operations, and activities. Those who had been in the college of more than 6 years were 16(14.3%) while 8 (7.1%) respondents had been in the college for less than 1 year.

Stakeholder Engagement and Performance of Southern New Hampshire University

This was the third objective of the study, which sought to establish the influence of stakeholder engagement on the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme. Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with various statements assessing how stakeholder engagement practices impact the performance of SNHU’s programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp, Turkana West, Kenya. Responses were rated on a Likert scale of 1 to 5, where; 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly Agree. The findings were summarized and presented in **Table 4.5**.

Table 4.2: Response on Stakeholder Engagement Practices

n=95

Stakeholder Engagement	SD		D		N		A		SA		Mean	Std. Dev
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Support services are siloed and not accessible to all stakeholders	9	9.5	1	20.9	2	23.2	2	29.8	1	17.9	3.26	1.20
Stake holders are alwaysinvolved in problemsolving efforts	4	4.2	8	8.4	1	16.6	4	44.2	2	26.3	3.80	1.03
Stakeholders are not engaged in solving problemsthat affect them	1	11.6	2	21.0	1	18.8	3	31.0	1	16.8	3.21	1.24
Decision making processes are clear transparent and inclusive	3	3.2	6	6.3	1	20.9	4	43.1	2	27.4	3.85	0.96
Stake holders do consultations before makingdecisions	5	5.3	7	7.4	1	15.5	4	45.3	2	26.3	3.80	1.01

Findings in Table 4.5 highlight stakeholder perspectives on how effectively Southern New Hampshire University engages its stakeholders in Kakuma Refugee Camp. The

analysis reveals both strengths and gaps in the university’s engagement practices. Regarding the statement “Support services are siloed and not accessible to all stakeholders,” a

total of 28 (29.5%) agreed and 17 (17.9%) strongly agreed, suggesting a notable portion of respondents perceive a lack of inclusive access. However, 19 (20.0%) disagreed, 9 (9.5%) strongly disagreed, and 22 (23.2%) remained neutral. The mean score was $M = 3.26$, with a relatively high standard deviation of $SD = 1.20$, indicating mixed perceptions. These results suggest that while support services are in place, access is inconsistent across different groups. This aligns with Anthony and Mukong (2022), who argue that fragmentation in service delivery weakens stakeholder engagement in refugee-based educational initiatives.

When asked whether stakeholders are always involved in problem-solving efforts, 42 (44.2%) agreed and 25 (26.3%) strongly agreed, while only 4 (4.2%) strongly disagreed, 8 (8.4%) disagreed, and 16 (16.8%) were neutral. The mean score of $M = 3.80$, with a standard deviation of $SD = 1.03$, indicates a high level of engagement in collaborative problem-solving. This suggests that SNHU provides platforms for stakeholders to participate meaningfully in addressing issues as they arise, consistent with Tripathi (2024), who emphasized that shared problem-solving enhances trust and ownership in development projects. On the negatively framed item, "Stakeholders are not engaged in solving problems that affect them," 30 (31.6%) agreed and 16 (16.8%) strongly agreed, while 18 (18.9%) remained neutral, and 31 (32.7%) disagreed or strongly disagreed. The mean score was $M = 3.21$, with a higher standard deviation of $SD = 1.24$, reflecting contradictory experiences. This item reveals that while many stakeholders feel excluded from solving relevant problems, others perceive adequate engagement. Such inconsistency may be due to differences in stakeholder categories (e.g., students vs. administrators), a finding that echoes Diniz (2025) who observed disparities in participatory practices within multi-stakeholder education systems.

On the item assessing whether decision-making processes are clear, transparent, and inclusive, the responses were overwhelmingly positive: 41 (43.2%) agreed and 26 (27.4%) strongly agreed, with only 3 (3.2%) strongly disagreeing, 6 (6.3%) disagreeing, and 19 (20.0%) neutral. The high mean of $M = 3.85$ and relatively low standard deviation of $SD =$

0.96 demonstrate strong consensus. This suggests that SNHU maintains transparent and participatory governance processes. As noted by Cao (2024), such practices improve institutional legitimacy and foster long-term stakeholder commitment.

Lastly, on whether stakeholders consult before making decisions, 43 (45.3%) agreed and 25 (26.3%) strongly agreed, while 15 (15.8%) were neutral, and only 5 (5.3%) strongly disagreed and 7 (7.4%) disagreed. The mean of $M = 3.80$, with a standard deviation of $SD = 1.01$, indicates that stakeholder consultation is a regular practice at SNHU. This aligns with Sakwe (2024) who argued that systematic consultation ensures decisions reflect diverse stakeholder interests and prevents conflict.

The findings show that SNHU generally performs well in stakeholder engagement, particularly in fostering transparency, inclusion in decision-making, and collaborative problem-solving. However, some concerns remain about unequal access to support services and occasional lapses in direct engagement, especially for certain groups. These results emphasize the need for SNHU to strengthen inclusive mechanisms and ensure consistent participation across all stakeholder categories.

Relationships Between the Independent and Dependent Variables

This section presents the inferential analysis used to assess the relationship between stakeholder management practices (independent variables) and the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme (dependent variable) in Kakuma Refugee Camp. Two key statistical techniques were employed: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis.

Pearson Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation was conducted to determine the degree of linear association between each of the four stakeholder management practices communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment and the performance of the SNHU programme. The results are summarized in Table 4.8 below.

Table 4.3: Pearson Correlation Analysis

Variable	r-value	Sig. (p-value)	Relationship
Stakeholder Communication	0.618	0.000	Strong, positive
Stakeholder Identification	0.537	0.000	Moderate, positive
Stakeholder Engagement	0.592	0.000	Strong, positive
Stakeholder Empowerment	0.568	0.000	Moderate, positive

The results in Table 4.8 indicate statistically significant positive correlations between all stakeholder management variables and the performance of SNHU ($p < 0.01$). The strongest relationship was found between stakeholder communication and performance ($r = 0.618$), suggesting that well-structured communication practices are closely associated with improved

programme outcomes. Stakeholder engagement also showed a strong relationship ($r = 0.592$), while identification and empowerment had moderate, yet meaningful associations ($r = 0.537$ and $r = 0.568$ respectively). These findings are consistent with those of Saima and Nadeem (2025) and Manzoor and Asmawi (2024) who found that stakeholder

involvement significantly boosts educational programme performance in fragile contexts.

Multiple Regression Analysis

A multiple regression model was used to assess the combined and individual influence of stakeholder management practices on SNHU’s programme performance. The model included the four stakeholder management dimensions as predictor variables. The results are presented in Table 4.9 below.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error
Regression	0.723	0.522	0.497	0.703

The model results presented in Table 4.9 yielded an R² value of 0.522, indicating that approximately 52.2% of the variance in performance of the SNHU programme can be explained by the combined stakeholder management practices. The Adjusted R² of 0.497 accounts for model complexity and confirms the model’s overall fitness.

Table 4.5: ANOVA

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p)
Regression	66.427	4	16.607	33.58	0.000
Residual	60.748	90	0.675		
Total	127.175	94			

The ANOVA results from the regression model (F = 33.58, p = 0.000) indicate that the model is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This means that the combined set of independent variables ; stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment significantly explain the variation in the dependent variable, which is the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme. This finding supports the core argument of the study that stakeholder management is not merely an administrative process, but a strategic contributor to institutional success, especially in fragile and resource-constrained environments like Kakuma Refugee Camp. The result shows that at least one, and likely several, of the stakeholder management practices (communication, engagement, identification, or empowerment) have a statistically meaningful impact on how well SNHU performs in delivering its academic mission in the camp.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	1.048	0.314	—	3.338	0.001
Stakeholder Communication	0.349	0.098	0.332	3.561	0.001
Stakeholder Identification	0.227	0.094	0.215	2.414	0.018
Stakeholder Engagement	0.319	0.096	0.287	3.323	0.001
Stakeholder Empowerment	0.198	0.092	0.190	2.152	0.034

The regression coefficients further confirm that all four stakeholder management practices have a statistically significant positive influence on SNHU performance (p < 0.05). Among them, stakeholder communication (β = 0.332) and stakeholder engagement (β = 0.287) emerged as the most influential predictors. This underscores the critical role of open communication channels and active stakeholder participation in enhancing program delivery, accountability, and learner satisfaction.

Discussion of the Findings

Stakeholder Engagement

Findings revealed that SNHU demonstrates generally strong stakeholder engagement practices in Kakuma Refugee Camp, particularly in areas of collaborative problem-solving and inclusive decision-making. Most stakeholders indicated that they are regularly consulted and involved in addressing issues, supporting Tripathi (2024), who highlights shared problem-solving as key to building trust and ownership in educational projects.

Respondents also expressed satisfaction with the clarity and transparency of decision-making processes, suggesting a well-structured governance approach. This aligns with Cao (2024), who notes that transparent institutional practices contribute to legitimacy and sustained stakeholder commitment.

However, concern emerged regarding unequal access to support services and inconsistent engagement across different stakeholder groups. Some respondents perceived service delivery as fragmented or inaccessible, which reflects the findings of Anthony and Mukong (2022) on the challenges of inclusivity in refugee education settings. Similarly, mixed responses on whether stakeholders are engaged in solving issues that affect them point to varying experiences across roles a concern echoed by Diniz (2025) in multi-stakeholder educational environments.

Performance of Southern New Hampshire University

The findings indicate that Southern New Hampshire University has largely met its institutional performance goals in Kakuma Refugee Camp, particularly in terms of academic relevance, practical skill application, and positive stakeholder perception.

Most respondents affirmed that SNHU’s programs meet the academic needs of learners, with a strong mean of M = 3.94. This consistency highlights the alignment between the curriculum and learner expectations, reflecting the importance of contextualized learning as emphasized by Saima & Nadeem (2025).

Similarly, the belief that SNHU graduates can apply acquired skills to solve real-life problems reflects high

satisfaction with the program's practicality ($M = 3.91$). This supports Manzoor and Asmawi (2024), who argue that competency-based learning is particularly effective in enhancing employability and resilience in marginalized settings.

The learning environment was also positively reviewed ($M = 3.81$), suggesting that SNHU has created relatively supportive academic conditions in a challenging refugee context consistent with Thomas (2025), who links effective delivery to strong infrastructure and instructional support.

In terms of community respect and program acceptance, findings show broad approval ($M = 3.77$), though with minor dissent. This reinforces Maniriho (2024)'s point that stakeholder legitimacy and trust are crucial for sustained educational impact in humanitarian settings.

However, student support services drew more varied opinions, with the lowest mean score ($M = 3.64$) and highest variability. While most respondents expressed satisfaction, others reported inconsistencies in accessing timely help echoing Samuel (2022), who highlighted the need for equitable and scalable support systems in remote education programs.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Stakeholder Engagement

Findings indicated that SNHU maintains strong engagement practices by involving stakeholders in decision-making and problem-solving efforts. The processes were perceived as transparent and inclusive, which contributes positively to institutional trust and ownership. Nonetheless, some stakeholders reported limited access to support services, reflecting inconsistencies in engagement across different groups. This points to the importance of enhancing the inclusivity of support mechanisms to ensure all stakeholders benefit equitably from engagement opportunities.

Theoretical Implications of the Study

The findings of this study have important theoretical implications for both Stakeholder Theory and Institutional Theory. Stakeholder Theory emphasizes that institutions should identify, engage, and respond to the needs of all stakeholders to enhance performance and legitimacy. This study confirms that SNHU's performance in Kakuma Refugee Camp is strongly influenced by how effectively it communicates with, identifies, engages, and empowers its stakeholders. The positive perceptions of structured communication, participatory decision-making, and risk management practices affirm the central premise of Stakeholder Theory that inclusive and responsive stakeholder engagement improves institutional outcomes.

Institutional Theory, which focuses on how organizational practices are shaped by norms, values, and external pressures, is also supported by the study. The findings suggest that SNHU has aligned its practices with the expectations of humanitarian and education-focused institutions by adopting participatory models of governance, policy transparency, and adaptive strategies in a refugee context. This indicates that SNHU's approach is influenced

not only by internal goals but also by external institutional pressures and norms within the higher education and humanitarian sectors. Therefore, the study contributes to the understanding of how institutional environments influence stakeholder management in challenging settings like refugee camps.

Implications of the Study Findings to Project Planning and Management

The study offers several practical implications for project planning and management, particularly in education projects implemented in humanitarian contexts. First, the importance of structured stakeholder communication emerged as a critical factor in enhancing coordination, trust, and accountability. Project managers should invest in stakeholder-driven communication strategies that are inclusive and culturally responsive.

Moreover, effective stakeholder identification based on both influence and capability proved essential to operational success. This implies that project planners should routinely reassess stakeholder roles to align with evolving project needs.

Furthermore, stakeholder engagement and empowerment were shown to contribute to improved problem-solving, legitimacy, and institutional performance. Therefore, planners must prioritize inclusive decision-making, transparent processes, and create mechanisms that allow stakeholders to influence project outcomes meaningfully.

Conclusions

The study concluded that stakeholder management practices specifically communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment significantly influence the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp. Stakeholders perceived SNHU's operations as largely inclusive, structured, and responsive to community needs. Communication practices were generally effective, though areas for improvement in responsiveness and consistency were identified. Stakeholder identification was impact-driven and skill-oriented, yet the evolving interests of stakeholders require closer monitoring. Engagement and empowerment efforts were positively received, but some inconsistencies suggest the need for more equitable application.

5.7 Recommendations

Based on the study findings on the influence of stakeholder communication, identification, engagement, and empowerment on the performance of the Southern New Hampshire University programme in Kakuma Refugee Camp, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. While existing stakeholder engagement mechanisms provide a foundation, there is an opportunity to enhance participatory decision-making within the program. SNHU can build on its current efforts by institutionalizing inclusive platforms that actively engage stakeholders in planning and dialogue. Regular mechanisms such as feedback forums, student councils and partner consultative meetings will help foster a culture of

inclusivity, shared ownership and collaborative problem-solving.

The study highlights an opportunity to enhance service delivery and program support to further strengthen the performance of the SNHU program. By routinely assessing the quality and accessibility of support services, SNHU can ensure they remain responsive to stakeholder needs. Coupling this with continuous monitoring and strong feedback mechanisms will help identify areas for improvement and drive more effective program performance.

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